

Establishment of an Desa Siaga to Improve Public Health Status during the New Normal Covid 19 Adaptive Period

Supadi¹, Ruti Wiyati², Ani Kuswati³

^{1,2,3}Politeknik Kesehatan Semarang, Indonesia

Email: supadispd73@gmail.com

Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic is a non-natural calamity that can have an influence on everyone's social and health situations. Some of the negative repercussions of COVID-19 on society are: health, economics, education, social and others. The purpose of this research is the establishment of an Desa Siaga and increasing public health status in the adaptive new normal Covid 19 mass, with the specific aim of obtaining an overview of public health after the Corona 19 pandemic, improving and re-activating village community health services, increasing public knowledge about health protocols in the New Normal era. The design of this research is "Quasy experimental pre-posttest with the intervention of the establishment of a standby village. The sample of this research is community leaders consisting of village officials, Citizens Association heads, village midwives, Karang Taruna, Family Welfare Empowerment consisting of 37 intervention groups and 37 control groups. Data analysis using paired. T-test. The results of this study Knowledge that there is an intervention group before 55.54 after 74.32. In the control group the average behavior before 54.46 after 55.27. The conclusion is that there is a significant difference in mental health before and after in the intervention group (p value 0.00), and there is no significant difference in the control group (p value 0.075).

Keywords: Covid 19, Desa Siaga, Health, Community.

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic is a man-made calamity that has the potential to affect everyone's social and health circumstances. According to World Health Organization (WHO) Director-General Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus, Friday 31-July 2020, the worldwide epidemic of Covid-19 is a form of calamity with a long-lasting impact. The Covid 19 pandemic has infected over 17 million people and killed over 670,000 deaths (Republica). A pandemic is a once-in-a-century health crisis, the impact of which will last for decades. Preliminary results from serological research (antibodies) show a consistent picture, namely that most of the world's people are still susceptible to the virus, even in areas that have experienced severe outbreaks (Webster et al., 2020| Morton et al., 2019; Foddai et al., 2020).

In Indonesia, it first confirmed the Covid outbreak on March 2, 2020. On March 15, Indonesia announced 117 cases, so that on March 31, Government Regulation No. 21 of 2020 which regulates PSPB (Large-Scale Social Restrictions) in response to Covid 19. The formation of the Covid 19 Task Force starting from the Neighborhood Association to Central level, and healthy living protocols starting from maintaining distance, mandatory wearing of masks and washing hands (Paul et al., 2021; Li et al., 2020). In early June, the government announced the enactment of New Normal for green zone areas while still using the healthy living protocol in the Covid era.

The covid curve tends to increase every day. As of August 21, 2020, Indonesia reported 2090 new cases of COVID-19, bringing the number of COVID-19 cases to 151,498. With 105,198 recovered cases and 6,594 deaths. For the Central Java region of 12,288 cases, 7931 recovered and 834 died. Some of the negative impacts due to COVID-19 on society are: health, economy, education, social and others.

The influence of the COVID-19 epidemic on the Indonesian labor market may be seen on the side of employees, enterprises, and individuals. The effect of layoffs and income loss. As many as 15.6 percent of workers were laid off, and 40% of workers had a loss in income, with 7 percent of workers' wages falling to 50%. This condition has a significant impact on employees' and their families' survival.

The pandemic of COVID-19 has had a significant influence on schooling in Indonesia. The short-term consequence is a shift in online learning techniques, which schools, instructors, students, and parents are acutely aware of. The unavailability of the internet network, electronic media, and the limitations of IT add to the complexity of educational problems. Meanwhile, the long-term impact is on the issue of justice and growing inequality within and across community groups and regions in Indonesia.

The continued high rate of new cases in Indonesia, as well as the magnitude of the Covid Pandemic's impact in Indonesia, are two of the primary reasons that researchers are interested in conducting research with the title; The

establishment of Desa Siaga to improve the community's health status in the new normal adaptive mass of covid 19.

Desa Siaga is a hamlet whose citizens possess the means, capabilities, and determination necessary to avoid and overcome health issues, catastrophes, and health emergencies on their own. If a hamlet already has at least one Village Health Post, it is referred to as a Desa Siaga.

Desa Siaga, as declared by the government, is an image of a community that is aware, willing, and capable of preventing and overcoming numerous dangers to public health, such as malnutrition, catastrophes, and mental diseases, via mutual collaboration. The main objective of developing Desa Siaga is to distribute basic health services to the community (Feter et al., 2021; Fahey et al., 2020; Boyle et al., 2020). For this reason, it is necessary to have community-based health efforts so that health efforts are more accessible, more affordable and more quality.

METHOD

This research is quantitative. The design used in this study was a "Quasy experimental pre-post test with an intervention for the establishment of a standby village. The establishment of a standby village began with a survey of village community health issues, village community consultations (MMD). After that, the Siaga village was formed, followed by conducting training on health adaptation in the new normal era for village officials, health cadres, youth organizations, Empowerment and Family Health and community leaders.

The sample in this study consisted of 74 respondents, of which 37 were the control group and 37 were the intervention group. To see the effect of knowledge before and after self-help groups were carried out using the paired t test.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of Respondents

The characteristics of the respondents in this study include gender, education and occupation. The description of the respondents' characteristics can be seen in table 1 below:

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents by Gender, Education and Occupation

Variable	Intervention		Control	
	F	%	F	%
Gender				
Male	15	40.5	16	43.2
Female	22	59.5	21	56.8
Total	37	100	37	100
Education				
Primary School	15	40.5	18	48.6
High School	20	54.1	17	45.9
College	2	5.4	2	5.4
Total	37	100	37	100
Profession				
Civil Servant	9	24.3	10	30
Farmer	15	16.2	17	45.9
Trader	6	16.2	2	5.4
Housewife	7	18.9	9	24.3
Total	37	100	37	100

Source: data proceed

According to Table 1, respondents in the intervention and control groups were mostly female, with 22 (59.5%) in the intervention group and 21 (56.8%) in the control group. Respondents in the intervention group had an average of 20 years of high school education (54.1 percent), whereas those in the control group had an average of 18 years of primary school education (48.6 percent). Then, respondents were classified according to their occupation, with the majority working as farmers (15 (40.5 percent) in the intervention group and mostly as farmers (17 (45.9 percent) in the control group, with the remainder working as traders and housewives in both the intervention and control groups.

According on the responses to the research, the majority of respondents were female. In reality, the volunteer workforce in the community is dominated by women, because women in the village have more free time than men (Britton et al., 2020). In addition, cadre activities are more focused on helping the community in the health sector, assessing the community that this work is more appropriate and appropriate for women. Although currently the elderly

posyandu is developing, the role of health cadres is still dominated by women. (Ung, 2020; Bauman et al., 2020; Nivette et al., 2021)

Based on the type of education occupation, most of the respondents have primary and secondary education. Kedungpring Village is an agricultural village, with lower-middle incomes. The community tends to send their children to at least basic education level. But there are some people who go to school up to the high school level, and up to a bachelor's degree. This is in accordance with the education level of the number of job seekers in Banyumas Regency that the education level of the workforce population aged over 15 years in Banyumas Regency in 2015 was partly elementary school education, namely as much as 55%. This impact affects the type of employment.

Public Health Knowledge in the New Normal Era

Public Health Knowledge in the New Normal Era in the intervention and control groups before the intervention (Wu et al., 2020; Paraskevis et al., 2021). Public health knowledge in the new normal era in the intervention and control groups before intervention can be seen in table 2 below:

Table 2. Public health knowledge in the new normal era of control and intervention groups before intervention

Group	n	Mean	SD
Control Intervension	37	54.46	6.212
	37	55.54	6.951

Source: data proceed

Based on table 2 shows that the average value of the control group, the level of public health knowledge in the New Normal Era is 54.46 lower than the intervention group, which is 55.54. Based on the results of research, some respondents have a misunderstanding of the public in the new normal era. Many people think that the Covid-19 pandemic is over. With the opening of public facilities such as: Malls, places of worship and several entertainment facilities, various people flocked to attend these places. Providing health support by involving key figures in the community: village officials, village midwives. Babinkantibmas, Health cadres, Neighborhood Association and Empowerment and Family Health can remind the public the importance of the Covid protocol in the New Normal era.

Based on the results of interviews with respondents, some people think that the corona pandemic has been successful and the incidence has decreased. But people remain vigilant using the new normal protocol.

Public Health Knowledge in the New Normal Era in the intervention and control groups after the intervention

Public health knowledge in the new normal era in the intervention and control groups after the intervention can be seen in table 3 below:

Table 3. Knowledge of public health in the new normal era of control and intervention groups after intervention

Group	n	Mean	SD
Control	37	55.27	6.309
Intervention	37	74.35	7.375

Source: data proceed

Based on the data in table 3, it can be seen that the average level of public health knowledge in the new normal era in the intervention group was 74.35 higher than the control group, which was 55.27.

Clear information can also increase the level of public knowledge. Counseling or providing information about mental health. This outreach activity is expected to increase public knowledge regarding the handling of mental disorders that occur in the community. The level of community knowledge is said to be good if it is able to answer questions about certain fields such as questions about mental health correctly and fluently both orally and in writing (Maqbool & Khan, 2020; Ali et al., 2020; Sapriya et al., 2021).

The factors that affect knowledge according to Notoatmodjo, (2015) include first, the level of education where the higher the level of education, the more knowledge will be and the information conveyed will be more easily absorbed. Second, information where someone who has a source of information with more knowledge will have extensive knowledge. Third, the culture in which a person's attitudes and beliefs about the information received. Fourth, experience where the more experience the knowledge will increase. Fifth, socio-economic where the higher the socioeconomic level, the higher the level of knowledge (Labolo, 2021).

In this era of information communication, the media cannot be left behind and plays a very important role in the successful delivery of information (Rahi et al., 2021). The media will help the general public and youth in particular

understand about the information we convey. In addition, the media can also help in overcoming many obstacles in understanding, for example if people do not understand something by looking at the media used by the community it will be easier to understand and understand (Ponsford et al., 2018; Aziz et al., 2020). Therefore, the media must be made as attractive as possible so that the public can understand the information conveyed.

The Influence of Public Health Education on the Formation of Desa Siaga on Public Health Knowledge in the New Normal Era

The influence of public health education on the establishment of an Desa Siaga on public health knowledge in the new normal era can be seen in table 4 below:

Table 4. The influence of public health education on the formation of an Desa Siaga on public health knowledge in the new normal era

Group	N	Mean	SD	SE	p value
Intervention	37				0.000
Before		55.54	6.951	1.43	
After		74.32	7.375	1.21	
Control	37				0.075
Before		54.46	6.212	1.02	
After		55.27	6.305	0.03	

Source: data proceed

According to Table 4, the intervention group's average level of public health knowledge in the New Normal Era was 55.54 prior to the intervention and 74.32 following the intervention. The statistical test returns a p value of 0.00, indicating that there is a statistically significant difference in knowledge between before and after the intervention.

While in the control group the average behavior before the results obtained was 54.46 and after the results obtained was 55.27. The statistical test resulted in a p value of 0.075, indicating that there was no statistically significant difference between before and after no intervention. The results of this study are in line with Rini Handayani's (2020) research on the impact of stressors on health workers and the community, that by providing mental health support can improve public health and reduce stress due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

According to Kinten Nafa's (2020) research, public health is critical in the new normal period for increasing awareness and good living behaviors.

WHO (2020) states that the advent of a pandemic creates stress at all levels of society. Although no comprehensive evaluation of the effect of COVID-19 on mental health has been conducted to yet, a number of studies associated to the pandemic (including avian influenza and SARS) have demonstrated a detrimental effect on the mental health of victims. According to research on SARS patients, 41-65 percent of survivors develop various types of psychiatric illnesses in the medium and long term (Halliday et al., 2015).

A research conducted in Hong Kong found that psychological issues experienced by SARS survivors did not resolve after a year of the outbreak. Indeed, it is projected that 64% of survivors may develop a psychological condition (Lee et al., 2007). Women and health care professionals are the two groups most at risk of experiencing various forms of psychological discomfort. Additionally, a Hong Kong research found that 30 months after SARS infection, 25.6 percent of survivors suffered from Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) and 15.6 percent from depression. At least 30% of survivors have at least one of these symptoms on average (Mak et al., 2009).

CONCLUSION

Based on the research objectives, the conclusions are as follows: 1) The characteristics of the respondents by gender are mostly women and the education level of the respondents is mostly high school education and the type of work of the respondents is mostly farmers; 2) The level of knowledge about mental health in the intervention group, obtained an average mental health knowledge before 54.44 and after 74.32, so it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the level of knowledge before and after the intervention (p value 0.00); and 3) The level of knowledge about mental health in the control group, the average mental health knowledge was 54.46 before and after 55.27 so it can be concluded that there was no significant difference before and after the intervention in the control group (p value 0.075).

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REFERENCES

- [1]. Ali, S. A., Baloch, M., Ahmed, N., Ali, A. A., & Iqbal, A. (2020). The Outbreak of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19)—An Emerging Global Health Threat. *Journal of infection and public health*, 13(4), 644-646.
- [2]. Aziz, N. A., Othman, J., Lugova, H., & Suleiman, A. (2020). Malaysia's Approach in Handling COVID-19 Onslaught: Report on the Movement Control Order (MCO) and Targeted Screening to Reduce Community Infection Rate and Impact on Public Health and Economy. *Journal of infection and public health*, 13(12), 1823-1829.
- [3]. Baumann, B. C., MacArthur, K. M., & Michalski, J. M. (2020). The Importance of Temporary Telehealth Parity Laws to Improve Public Health during COVID-19 and Future Pandemics. *International Journal of Radiation Oncology, Biology, Physics*, 108(2), 362-363.
- [4]. Boyle, C. A., Fox, M. H., Havercamp, S. M., & Zubler, J. (2020). The Public Health Response to the COVID-19 Pandemic for People with Disabilities. *Disability and Health Journal*, 13(3), 100943.
- [5]. Britton, P. N., Hu, N., Saravanos, G., Shrapnel, J., Davis, J., Snelling, T., ... & Lingam, R. (2020). COVID-19 Public Health Measures and Respiratory Syncytial Virus. *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health*, 4(11), e42-e43.
- [6]. Fahey, R. A., & Hino, A. (2020). COVID-19, Digital Privacy, and the Social Limits on Data-Focused Public Health Responses. *International Journal of Information Management*, 55, 102181.
- [7]. Feter, N., Caputo, E. L., Doring, I. R., Leite, J. S., Cassuriaga, J., Reichert, F. F., ... & Rombaldi, A. J. (2021). Sharp Increase in Depression and Anxiety among Brazilian Adults during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Findings from the PAMPA Cohort. *Public health*, 190, 101-107.
- [8]. Foddai, A., Lindberg, A., Lubroth, J., & Ellis-Iversen, J. (2020). Surveillance To Improve Evidence for Community Control Decisions during the COVID-19 Pandemic—Opening the Animal Epidemic Toolbox for Public Health. *One Health*, 9, 100130.
- [9]. Halliday, E., Orton, L., Egan, M., Lewis, S., Powell, K., Townsend, A., ... & Popay, J. (2015). Understanding Area-Based Community Empowerment Initiatives as Events in Systems and the Implications for Evaluating Their Potential to Affect Health Inequalities. *The Lancet*, 386, S41.
- [10]. Health, T. L. P. (2020). COVID-19 Puts Societies to the Test. *The Lancet. Public Health*, 5(5), e235.
- [11]. Labolo, M. (2021). Government Policy in Handling Stunting and Malnutrition in Children during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Ayer Journal*, 28(1), 80-99.
- [12]. Li, Q., Tang, B., Bragazzi, N. L., Xiao, Y., & Wu, J. (2020). Modeling the Impact of Mass Influenza Vaccination and Public Health Interventions on COVID-19 Epidemics with Limited Detection Capability. *Mathematical biosciences*, 325, 108378.
- [13]. Maqbool, A., & Khan, N. Z. (2020). Analyzing Barriers for Implementation of Public Health and Social Measures to Prevent the Transmission of COVID-19 Disease using DEMATEL Method. *Diabetes & Metabolic Syndrome: Clinical Research & Reviews*, 14(5), 887-892.
- [14]. Morton, S., Pencheon, D., & Bickler, G. (2019). The Sustainable Development Goals Provide an Important Framework for Addressing Dangerous Climate Change and Achieving Wider Public Health Benefits. *Public Health*, 174, 65-68.
- [15]. Nivette, A., Ribeaud, D., Murray, A., Steinhoff, A., Bechtiger, L., Hepp, U., ... & Eisner, M. (2021). Non-Compliance with COVID-19-Related Public Health Measures among Young Adults in Switzerland: Insights from a Longitudinal Cohort Study. *Social science & medicine*, 268, 113370.
- [16]. Notoatmodjo, S. (2015). *Pendidikan dan Perilaku Kesehatan*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta
- [17]. Paraskevis, D., Kostaki, E. G., Alygizakis, N., Thomaidis, N. S., Cartalis, C., Tsiodras, S., & Dimopoulos, M. A. (2021). A Review of the Impact of Weather and Climate Variables to COVID-19: In the Absence of Public Health Measures High Temperatures cannot Probably Mitigate Outbreaks. *Science of the Total Environment*, 768, 144578.
- [18]. Paul, E., Steptoe, A., & Fancourt, D. (2021). Attitudes towards Vaccines and Intention to Vaccinate Against COVID-19: Implications for Public Health Communications. *The Lancet Regional Health-Europe*, 1, 100012.
- [19]. Ponsford, R., Halliday, E., Collins, M., Egan, M., Scott, C., & Popay, J. (2018). Area Reputation as an Under-Acknowledged Determinant of Health Inequalities: Evidence from a Systems Evaluation of a Major Community Empowerment Initiative in England. *The Lancet*, 392, S72.
- [20]. Rahi, M., Ahmad, S. S., & Sharma, A. (2021). Coverage Enhancement and Community Empowerment via Commercial Availability of the Long-Lasting Nets for Malaria in India. *Public Health in Practice*, 2, 100133.
- [21]. Sapriya, S., Fitriyari, S., Syaifullah, S., Masyitoh, I. S., Fauzi, A., & Kurniaty, N. R. D. (2021, February). Community Empowerment Model to Develop Civic Virtue Towards Communal Health as an Effort to Tackle the Spread of

Pandemic (A study on School Program 'Siaga Covid'at SMAN 7 Bandung). In *1st International Conference on Character Education (ICCE 2020)* (pp. 223-227). Atlantis Press.

- [22]. Ung, C. O. L. (2020). Community Pharmacist in Public Health Emergencies: Quick to Action against the Coronavirus 2019-nCoV Outbreak. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy, 16*(4), 583-586.
- [23]. Webster, R. K., Brooks, S. K., Smith, L. E., Woodland, L., Wessely, S., & Rubin, G. J. (2020). How to Improve Adherence with Quarantine: Rapid Review of the Evidence. *Public health, 182*, 163-169.
- [24]. Wu, H. L., Huang, J., Zhang, C. J., He, Z., & Ming, W. K. (2020). Facemask Shortage and the Novel Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) Outbreak: Reflections on Public Health Measures. *EClinicalMedicine, 21*, 100329.